

A MICROMECHANICAL APPROACH TO STUDY THE DAMAGE EVOLUTION OF EPOXY BASED COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

In this contribution, a novel approach to study the matrix crack evolution on a micromechanical level is introduced. For the micromechanical analysis, material models for the fibers, the matrix, and the fiber-matrix-interface are needed.

In uniaxial mechanical tests, the epoxy based resin is found to behave viscoplastically. A rheological model is developed and calibrated using cyclic tensile test data. Uniaxial fatigue tests are used to derive a direction-independent failure criterion based on the hysteresis energy. While the interface properties are set to be equal with the neat resin ones, the fibers are idealized to behave elastically and with no damage.

Utilizing a cycle jump and degradation framework, an RVE of a fiber-reinforced composite is created. The damage observed in the RVE shows a single, dominant crack perpendicular to the loading direction with a distinct degradation of the effective stiffness in the loading direction. Further investigations regarding the element, and cycle jump size as well as the fiber architecture (volume fraction, radius, RVE size, ...) are identified as next steps.

1 INTRODUCTION

Numerous approaches to model the fatigue behavior of fiber-reinforced composites have been developed in the past. A thorough overview of available models is given in [1]. As in the static damage and failure assessment, the high number of models expresses the complexity of the behavior and shows a high degree of specialization. With the micromechanical basis not fully understood and incorporated, most models lack a great deal of generality, i.e. cannot be applied to other materials/layups/structures than what they have been developed for.

With modern imaging technologies like highly energetic x-ray tomography, the micromechanical nature of damage development is being focused on in recent studies [2-4]. This contribution introduces a micromechanical modelling strategy to investigate the damage initiation and evolution of transverse cracks on a fiber/matrix scale. To achieve this, three components are needed:

1. A material model for the resin and interface including a degradation rule
2. A material model for the fibers, optionally including a degradation rule
3. A representative, parametric, and adjustable fe-model of the micro-scale architecture

First, the phenomenology of the material under static and cyclic loading conditions is identified and introduced. This behavior is then modelled mathematically, and the material properties as well as a degradation rule are determined. The micromechanical model is derived and first results of the cyclic crack evolution behavior are presented.

2 MATERIAL BEHAVIOR OF AN EPOXY BASED RESIN

2.1 Quasistatic behavior

Materials can be classified by rate-dependency and the type of loading/unloading behavior. A rate-independent material with no hysteresis is generally known as an elastic material whereas a rate-independent material with hysteresis is labelled plastic. Rate-dependent models can be viscoplastic or viscoelastic depending on showing an equilibrium hysteresis or not.

For a categorization of the material behavior, tension tests at different rates, tension tests with intermediate relaxation, as well as cyclic tests are performed on the epoxy resin system LY564/Aradur22962.

Performing displacement controlled tensile tests at different displacement rates, a clear dependency on the loading rate can be observed as seen in Figure 1. Compared to other polymer systems, the thermoset epoxy shows comparatively small failure strains of around 5 % decreasing with increasing loading-rate.

Figure 1: Tensile test data at different displacement rates.

Figure 2: Intermediate relaxation test. Left: Strain-time specification, right: Resulting stress-strain-relation.

To determine which type of time-dependent material behavior is present, intermediate relaxation tests are performed. That is, a loading-unloading cycle at 10 mm/s is interrupted by 4-hour relaxation periods as seen in Figure 2. The connection of the equilibrium points is called the equilibrium relation, which describes the material's response to an infinitesimal small loading rate. As the equilibrium relation shows a hysteresis, the material can be characterized to behave viscoplastically. However, due

to the uniqueness of the first loading cycle compared to the stabilized cyclic response, the mathematical material model may differ from the phenomenological characterization.

2.2 Cyclic behavior

Cyclic tensile tests at 5 Hz with a ratio of lower to upper stress (R-ratio) of 0.1 are conducted to characterize the fatigue behavior material. The failure in the cyclic tests is sudden death like. No signs of cracking or translucency changes in the specimens is observed during the loading. The load-displacement history reveals that there is no change in stiffness until final failure, which backs the visual observations.

The most straightforward result to evaluate is the stress amplitude versus number of cycles to failure relation known as S-N or Wöhler diagram, Figure 3. Each point in this diagram represents a cyclic test with an entire set of load and displacement history data. A cycle-by-cycle analysis reveals that the hysteresis energy for each cycle reaches a stabilized value and remains constant until final failure.

Figure 3: S-N diagram also known as Wöhler diagram

Figure 4: Energy measures and their relation to the number of cycles to failure. Left: Stabilized hysteresis energy per cycle, right: Accumulated hysteresis energy

Interestingly, the energy accumulated until failure increases with increasing number of cycles to failure as shown in Figure 4. That is, the higher the stress level, the less energy is accumulated by hysteresis.

The (stabilized) hysteresis energy per cycle versus the number of cycles to failure shows a similar behavior as the S-N diagram. Note, that the hysteresis energy is a scalar measure, and therefore is of inherent multiaxial nature suitable for a straightforward energy-based failure criterion.

3 MATHEMETICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE MATERIAL AND DAMAGE BEHAVIOR

3.1 Material model

Rheological elements can describe complex material behavior in a modular and vivid manner. If assembled in parallel, the sum of stresses of each sub-model yields the total stress of the material. Kästner et al. [5] use a nonlinear elastic, a plastic, and a nonlinear viscous sub-model to describe the nonlinear static behavior of fiber-reinforced polypropylene. Fitting the equilibrium relation with the elasto-plastic model and the viscous parameters via relaxation and tension tests, his model tends to overestimate the stabilized hysteresis. The first cycle is used to obtain the equilibrium relation, which acts as a rate-independent backbone for the material response. This first cycle, however, does not seem to be representative for the stabilized cyclic response. Drozdov and Christiansen [6] circumvent this issue by switching models from the first to the following cycles and by differentiating loading and unloading behavior. While the latter model can describe the material behavior well for a wide range of loading conditions, the fitting of the material parameters is much more complex. Therefore, in this contribution a modular model is used. The focus of the parameter fitting is to describe the stabilized cyclic response of the material neglecting the static behavior to certain extends. Additionally, since the hysteresis of the equilibrium relation cannot be used for the plastic sub-model fitting due to the uniqueness of the virgin cycle, the plastic sub-model is not used. The parameters of the plastic sub-model cannot be identified unambiguously. The hysteresis observed in the cyclic tests is thus idealized to originate from viscous effects, only.

The uniaxial nonlinear elastic sub-model used by Kästner et al. [5] reads

$$\sigma_{elas} = \frac{E_1}{1 + \alpha|\varepsilon|} \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

with E_1, α being material parameters and $\sigma_{elas}, \varepsilon$ the elastic part of the stress and the total strain, respectively. This sub-model is thermodynamically consistent and converges to $\sigma_{elas,\infty} = E_1/\alpha$ for large strains.

For the rate dependent part of the material model, a series of Maxwell elements each consisting of a linear spring and a linear dashpot element is the most straightforward way of modelling. The stress response of a Maxwell element i can be derived from the basic rules of series connection in which the stresses remain equal while the strains are split up into an elastic $\varepsilon_{e,i}$ and a dashpot strain q_i which acts as an inner variable. The stress of the Maxwell element reads

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{e,i} + q_i \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{MW,i} = E_{3,i}\varepsilon_{e,i} = E_{3,i}(\varepsilon - q_i), \quad (3)$$

with $E_{3,i}$ representing the stiffness of the spring. For a classical Maxwell element, the evolution equation for the inner variable reads

$$\dot{q}_i = \frac{E_{3,i}}{\eta_i}(\varepsilon - q_i) = \frac{\sigma_{MW,i}}{\eta_i}, \quad (4)$$

with η_i denoting the dashpot viscosity parameter. The linear relationship between the dashpot strain rate and the stress of the Maxwell element is a strong idealization of polymer behavior and found valid only for small strains in the tension tests performed. To account for this behavior, the evolution equation of the inner variable is modified using a hyperbolic sine approach

$$\dot{q}_i = A_i \sinh(B_i \sigma_{MW,i}), \quad (5)$$

with A_i, B_i denoting the new material parameters of the dashpot. Calculating the derivative of eq. (3) with respect to the time and replacing the rate of the inner variable using eq. (5) yields the

differential equation of the nonlinear Maxwell element

$$\dot{\sigma}_{MW,i} = E_{3,i}\dot{\varepsilon} - E_{3,i}A_i \sinh(B_i\sigma_{MW,i}). \quad (6)$$

Figure 5 shows the complete rheological network of the material model. From the assembly, the split of stresses into sub-model stresses can be interpreted very easily.

Figure 5: Energy measures and their relation to the number of cycles to failure. Left: Stabilized hysteresis energy per cycle, right: Accumulated hysteresis energy

3.1 Fitting of material parameters

To fit the material parameters, a framework is developed to calculate stresses from arbitrary strain-time-data using Python and Qt (PySide). Incorporating various optimization algorithms available through the SciPy package, a nonlinear least square fit is performed. To calculate the stresses, a mathematical discretization of the nonlinear differential equation (6) is necessary. To this end, the second order precise and implicit midpoint rule is used. The equation is evaluated at time $t + \Delta t/2$ so that the time derivatives read

$$\dot{()}\big|_{t+\Delta t/2} \approx \frac{t+\Delta t() - t()}{\Delta t} =: \frac{t+\Delta()}{\Delta t}, \quad (7)$$

and the function values read

$$()_{t+\Delta t/2} \approx t() + \frac{1}{2} t+\Delta(), \quad (8)$$

with the $t+\Delta()$ values being unknown. The discretized differential equation (6) then reads

$$\frac{t+\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}}{\Delta t} = E_{3,i} \frac{t+\Delta\varepsilon}{\Delta t} - E_{3,i}A_i \sinh\left(B_i\left(t\sigma_{MW,i} + \frac{1}{2}t+\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}\right)\right) =: f(t+\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}), \quad (9)$$

with the stress increment $t+\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}$ being unknown and the strain and time increments $t+\Delta\varepsilon$, Δt given by the time integration framework. This implicit algebraic equation is solved using a fixed-point-iteration scheme

$$n+1\Delta\sigma_{MW,i} = f(n\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}), \quad (10)$$

with the starting value $0\Delta\sigma_{MW,i}$ obtained from an explicit Euler-forward discretization of (6)

$$0\Delta\sigma_{MW,i} = E_{3,i}t+\Delta\varepsilon - E_{3,i}A_i\Delta t \sinh\left(B_i(t\sigma_{MW,i})\right). \quad (11)$$

The smaller the time increment, the less difference between the starting solution and the iteration result is observed. For reasonably large time increments, however, the explicit Euler-scheme suffers from stability issues and inaccurate stress calculations leading to unphysical results.

The fitting framework tool is used to first fit the ascending part of the equilibrium hysteresis with the nonlinear elastic sub-model. The parameters identified are listed in Table 1.

Figure 6: Screenshot from the fitting framework tool after the fitting of the nonlinear elastic sub-model

Inspired by DMA measurements, the parameters of the nonlinear Maxwell elements are fitted through cyclic tests at different frequencies, namely 0.6 Hz and 2 Hz. In the time domain, the determination of viscous parameters is limited by the imperfect load application in real relaxation experiments. While theoretically, a Heaviside strain loading needs to be applied to the material to capture the effects of all Maxwell elements, in reality a finite time span is needed to apply the load thus leading to a cut of all Maxwell elements with characteristic times smaller than the load application time span. Fitting through a range of cyclic experiments allows the fit of Maxwell elements within a wide range of characteristic times. Figure 7 shows the results of the viscous fit.

Figure 7: Fits of the stabilized cycle. Left: 0.6 Hz, Right: 2 Hz.

For the material model to be used in an FE-analysis, the model is generalized to multiaxial loading conditions introducing a Poisson's ratio of $\nu = 0.4$. To this end, the stresses are split into a deviatoric and volumetric part introducing additional material parameters, which are, however, dependent of one another. Their relationship to one another is obtained from a coefficient comparison as the uniaxial model and the multiaxial model under uniaxial loading must yield the same stress result.

While this procedure is straight-forward for the elastic sub-model, the generalization of the nonlinear viscous sub-model, i.e. the relationship between the deviatoric and volumetric material constants with respect to the uniaxial ones, is more complicated and cannot be described in short within the scope of this work.

Material property	Unit	Fitted value
E_1	[MPa]	3646
α	[-]	46.8
$E_{3,1}$	[MPa]	166
A_1	[1/s]	2.364e-02
B_1	[1/MPa]	1.0
$E_{3,2}$	[MPa]	520.2
A_2	[1/s]	2.456e-02
B_2	[1/MPa]	9.638e-04

Table 1: Identified material parameters

3.2 Degradation procedure based on the hysteresis energy

As stated before, the hysteresis energy is a direction-independent measure for the level of loading in multiaxial loading conditions. A failure criterion can be derived based on the stabilized hysteresis energy in this cycle. A cycle-by-cycle numerical analysis is extraordinarily resource demanding and thus not feasible. Instead, cycle jump algorithms can be used to significantly reduce the computational effort. As the loading and thus the hysteresis energy can change during the analysis due to stress redistributions, a linear damage accumulation rule (Miner's rule) is utilized. Figure 8 shows the general procedure for the degradation. After the stresses and the stabilized hysteresis energy are calculated for the material point, a cycle jump Δn is imposed and the total number of cycles to failure N_f at the current hysteresis energy is determined based on the experimental relation. Following Miner's rule, the relative life RL can be updated

$$RL = RL + \frac{\Delta n}{N_f}. \quad (12)$$

If this parameter exceeds the value of one, the material point is degraded to a zero-stiffness thus returning 0-stresses for the rest of the analysis.

Figure 8: Flowchart of the degradation procedure

4 MICROSCALE MODELING AND RESULTS

Vaughan and McCarthy [7] present a toolbox for the generation of statistically representative volume elements (sRVE). It is found that RVE with entirely random fiber distributions yield almost equivalent results to sRVE if a) the RVE contains a similar amount of fibers and b) the fiber volume fractions are equal. Adding flexibility to the framework, the statistical representativeness is sacrificed towards an adjustable tool that generates RVE with a pre-set fiber volume fraction. The periodicity of the geometry as well as of the boundary conditions is enforced. To this end, an Abaqus plugin is developed which lets the user set all relevant parameters for the RVE generation such as sizes and elementation settings as well as fiber volume fraction and material properties.

The numerical evaluation of a transverse crack growth is the main target of this study. The fibers are therefore assumed ideally elastic (isotropic glass fibers, $E = 77$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$) and the load case is chosen so that no damage in the fibers is expected. The damage behavior of fiber-matrix-interface, on the other hand, is crucial regarding the global damage behavior, which is also shown in [7]. Here, the same mechanical but optionally different damage behavior is assumed as for the neat resin. In parametric studies, the influence of the interface strength can then be estimated by adjusting the according damage parameters.

For demonstration purposes, an RVE is created containing 64 fibers resulting in a fiber volume fraction of 49.6 %. A transverse, force controlled, cyclic, 5 Hz load of 20 MPa is applied. The cycle jumps are distributed logarithmically. Figure 9 shows the resulting effective strain which acts as a measure for the compliance increase due to damage in the RVE: Additionally, the contour plots of the damage in the RVE at certain points in time are displayed. Even though multiple interfaces are damaged throughout the RVE, a single dominant crack¹ perpendicular to the loading direction forms leading to a noticeable degradation of the effective material stiffness in this direction. Mesh refinement studies as well as the influence of the cycle jump on the global stiffness history still needs to be investigated.

Figure 9: History of effective strain vs. cycle number until failure including damage variable contour plots at different points in time.

¹ Note that the term „crack“ in this context refers to the connection of fully degraded elements through continuum damage mechanics and does not represent a crack in a fracture mechanical viewpoint.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The mechanical properties of an epoxy-based resin are investigated under static and cyclic tension conditions. Due to the loading-rate-dependence of the stress response and the presence of an equilibrium hysteresis unveiled by inter-relaxation tests, the material behavior observed can be labeled viscoplastic. Seen in the cyclic results, the maximum accumulated hysteresis energy depends on the load level. As there is no stiffness degradation, the stabilized hysteresis energy is a direction-independent measure for the load level and can be correlated with the number of cycles to failure.

A rheological model is fitted to describe the stabilized hysteresis of the polymer. Due to the uniqueness of the first loading cycle, the plastic portion of the material cannot be identified well enough for a model fit. As a result, a viscoelastic model is used to describe the mechanical response of the epoxy. The hysteresis energy is used as the physical basis for a degradation procedure, which is incorporated in a 3D RVE with random fiber distribution to model the crack initiation and evolution of transverse cracks in a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite material.

As this contribution is to introduce the framework and the general procedure to study the transverse crack initiation and growth, detailed analyses of the effect of the interface strength, the fiber volume fraction or the fiber distribution on the damage behavior remain an open task. In addition, a possible transition of the results between the different scales, i.e. from the current micro scale to the macro scale needs to be reviewed.

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